

Kinetics of bromination of substituted acetophenones by phenyltrimethylammonium tribromide

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Bromination of different ketones in glacial acetic acid by phenyltrimethylammonium tribromide (PTT) using sulfuric acid as catalyst at different temperature has been carried out. The study shows first order kinetics due to ketones and inverse first order kinetics due to PTT. The thermodynamic parameters are evaluated. The products of bromination of different acetophenones are found to be monobromoacetophenones.

Organic bromo derivatives are well known for their biological activities¹. The bromo derivatives are widely used as reactive intermediates in various organic synthesis. Clinically important heterocyclic compounds like thiazoles, benzthiazoles, 1,4-benzothiazines etc. can be obtained from α -bromocarbonyl compounds². Bromination of different organic compounds by various brominating agents has been studied. The effect of substituents has been studied with the help of thermodynamic parameters. However due to the lack of general method for treating cumulative effects of multiple substituents, most outstanding deviations are assigned to some specific interactions. The present communication reports kinetic study of bromination of substituted acetophenone using PTT as brominating agent.

Results and Discussion

The results of bromination of substituted acetophenones by PTT are presented in Tables 1–6.

Table 1. Dependence of rate constant on [PTT]
[Substrate] = $3.5 \times 10^{-3} M$, $H_2SO_4 = 0.60 N$, Temp. = 303 K

[PTT] $\times 10^3 M$	$k \times 10^3 s^{-1}$			
	NH ₂ AP	PhAP	AP	BrAP
3.5	1.352	1.117	1.020	0.790
3.0	1.611	1.371	1.119	1.160
2.5	2.182	1.866	1.239	1.319
2.0	2.527	2.068	1.387	1.631

Table 2 Dependence of rate constant on [Substrate]
[PTT] = $3.5 \times 10^{-3} M$, $H_2SO_4 = 0.60 N$, Temp. = 303 K

[Subs.] $\times 10^3 M$	$k \times 10^3 s^{-1}$			
	NH ₂ AP	PhAP	AP	BrAP
3.5	9.245	1.136	1.020	0.973
3.0	7.392	0.965	0.888	0.735
2.5	6.239	0.728	0.739	0.642
2.0	5.460	0.489	0.629	0.513

Table 3. Dependence of rate constant on $[H_2SO_4]$

[Substrate] = $3.5 \times 10^{-3} M$, [PTT] = $3.5 \times 10^{-3} M$, Temp. = 303 K

$[H_2SO_4]$	0.30	0.45	0.60	0.75	0.90 N
NH ₂ AP $k \times 10^4 s^{-1}$	4.35	5.32	7.04	10.77	11.58
PhAP $k \times 10^4 s^{-1}$	0.63	0.96	1.33	1.55	1.75

Table 4. Effects of ionic strength on rate constant

[Substrate] = $3.5 \times 10^{-3} M$, [PTT] = $3.5 \times 10^{-3} M$, $[H_2SO_4] = 0.60 N$, Temp. = 303 K

$[CH_3COONa] 10^{-3} M$	0.00	2.5	5.0	7.5	10.0
$K \times 10^3 M s^{-1}$	3.18	4.89	7.47	11.10	14.69

Table 5. Temperature effect on bromination of substituted acetophenones
[Substrate] = $3.5 \times 10^{-3} M$, $H_2SO_4 = 0.60 N$, [PTT] = $3.5 \times 10^{-3} M$, $k \times 10^3 mol dm^{-3} s^{-1}$, Temp. = 303 K

Substrate	303	308	313	318 K
NH ₂ AP	1.352	1.105	4.301	6.950
PhAP	1.147	1.906	2.792	4.402
AP	1.020	1.246	1.535	1.893
BrAP	0.963	1.105	1.315	1.514

Table 6. Thermodynamic parameters

[Substrate] = $3.5 \times 10^{-3} M$, $H_2SO_4 = 0.60 N$, [PTT] = $3.5 \times 10^{-3} M$, Temp. = 303 K

Substrate	Frequency factor (A) $dm^3 mol^{-1} s^{-1}$	E_a kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔH^\ddagger kJ mol ⁻¹	$-\Delta S^\ddagger$	ΔG^\ddagger kJ mol ⁻¹
NH ₂ AP	2.37×10^4	41.81	39.33	161.28	87.39
PhAP	1.21×10^7	61.32	58.84	109.39	91.44
AP	1.02×10^8	76.43	64.95	091.67	92.27
BrAP	3.89×10^8	70.75	68.27	080.68	92.35

The order was inverse first order with respect to [PTT]. The plot of log k against log [PTT] with a negative slope indicates that the rate constant is inversely proportional to

[PTT] due to decrease in concentration of reactive species^{3,4}. The plot of $1/k$ against $1/[PTT]$ does not pass through the origin indicating the formation of intermediate complex. The order with respect to substrate was also one as revealed by unit slope of the plot of $\log k$ against \log [substrate]. The plot of $1/k$ against $1/\log$ [substrate] was also linear with intercept on the Y-axis, suggesting the complex formation between reactant molecules. The rate of reaction increased with increase in $[H_2SO_4]$. The plot of $\log k$ vs $\log [H^+]$ was linear with unit slope. The rate constant increases with increase in dielectric constant of the medium. The distance between two interacting ions has been calculated from the slope of $\log k$ vs $1/D$ plot of bromoacetophenone. The value was found to be 5.5 Å, in agreement with Laidler's predictions⁵.

The plot of $\log k$ vs square-root of ionic strength was linear with positive slope. The trend indicates that the reacting species are ionic with same charges⁶, hence as the ionic strength increases the rate constant increases. The rate of reaction increases with increase in temperature according to Arrhenius equation. The relatively small ΔH^\ddagger and negative ΔS^\ddagger are consistent with highly organized transition state^{7,8}. The negative values of entropy of activation indicate that the reaction involves the transfer of electron between ions of the same charge⁹. The slopes at 338 and 346 K obtained from the linear plots of ΔH^\ddagger vs ΔS^\ddagger and E_a vs $\log A$, respectively, are in agreement with the values obtained from $\log k$ vs $1/T$ plot. That the isokinetic temperature is greater than the experimental temperature, indicates that the reactions are entropy-controlled. The values of entropy of activation also suggest that the reaction is free entropy as well as enthalpy controlled. The values of free energies of activation of the reaction were found to be more or less similar. This trend also supports the identical reaction mechanism being followed in these reactions. The slope at 342 K for linear relationship in Exner plot of $4 + \log k_2$ (308 K) vs $4 + \log k_1$ (303 K) observed in the present study also supports the conclusion drawn from isokinetic temperature.

Mechanism

Scheme 1

Based on the above experimental observation, a probable mechanism (Scheme 1) is suggested and the rate law is derived as

$$\frac{dx}{dt} \propto \frac{[\text{Substrate}][\text{Acid}]}{[\text{PTT}]}$$

The effect of substituents on rate was studied by varying the substituents in acetophenone. The order of reactivities with substituents in acetophenone is *p*-aminoacetophenone > *p*-phenylacetophenone > acetophenone > *p*-bromoacetophenone. Electron-withdrawing groups decrease the rate of bromination while the electron-donating groups increase the process. The electron-donating group donates the electrons by resonance, increases the relative stability of the keto form and shows higher reactivity.

The Hammett's constants were determined by plotting rate constant against σ values of various substituents. The linear nature of plot supports the identical mechanism in all the bromination reactions. The change in rate of reaction with respect to change in substituents was studied. An interesting observation is that the base-catalyzed bromination reactions give a mixture of mono-, di- and tribromo derivatives of acetophenones, while in the present work the reaction gives only monobromoacetophenone derivatives.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. The substituted acetophenone were prepared by standard method¹⁰. Glacial acetic acid was purified by literature procedure¹¹. PTT was prepared by standard procedure¹². The purity of substituted acetophenones and PTT were checked by TLC and elemental analysis.

Solutions of brominating reagent, 3*N* H_2SO_4 (2 ml) and substrate were heated separately in a thermostat in requisite proportions for 1 h. The solutions were then mixed with shaking to initiate the reaction. Aliquots of the reaction mixture were drawn at different time intervals and the absorbance of PTT at 405 nm was measured using acetic acid as a solvent. The reaction rate was studied upto 75% completion of the reaction. The rate constants were determined and activation and thermodynamic parameters calculated (Tables 1–6). The product of the reaction was analyzed and confirmed by m.p. and TLC.

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References

1. R. A. Mane, Ph.D. Thesis, Dr. B. A. M. University, Aurangabad, 1981.
2. A. R. Sawale, Ph.D. Thesis, Dr. B. A. M. University, Aurangabad,

- 1996.
3. K. Ganpathy and C. Ilango, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1986, **62**, 1052.
4. V. S. Shrinivasan and N. Venkatasubramanian, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1970, **8**, 57.
5. K. J. Laidler, "Chemical Kinetics", Tata-McGraw Hill, New Delhi, 1986, p. 214.
6. G. Scatchard, *Chem. Rev.*, 1932, **10**, 224.
7. E. V. Sundaram, G. V. S. Shaidhar and M. J. Satyanarayana, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1988, **65**, 346.
8. S. C. Basu, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1984, **23**, 884.
9. N. Sutin and J. K. Yandell, *J. Biochem.*, 1977, **16**, 1741.
10. A. I. Vogel, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 1814.
11. K. S. P. Orton and A. E. Bradfield, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 983.
12. Noland, *Org. Synth.*, 1988, **6**, 175.